

Molybdenum: Part II. Pyridine Carboxylic Acid Complexes of Oxo-Molybdenum (V)

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A number of pyridine mono- and di-carboxylic acids have been investigated as co-ordinating ligands towards oxo-molybdenum (V). The following complexes are reported:

- (1) $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{Pic})_2]$; (2) $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{Pic}/\text{Quin H}/\text{Nic}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$; (3) $[(\text{MoO}_2 \text{ Pic}) \text{H}_2\text{O}]$; (4) $(\text{MoO}_2 \text{ Nic}) 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; (5) $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{Lut}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$; and (6) $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{Pic})(\text{tu})]$

(PicH) = Picolinic acid, NicH = Nicotinic acid; QuinH = Quinolinic acid; LutH = Lutidinic acid & tu = Thiourca).

The complexes are all highly coloured, crystalline and stable to air. They are either diamagnetic or show very low magnetic susceptibility. The complexes being insoluble, the reflectance spectra have been obtained in a few cases and these discussed in terms of prevailing ideas.

In the preceding part of this series¹, we have presented the background that had led us to undertake these studies in our laboratory. A brief summary of the prevailing types of oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes has also been given. Several types of oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes with quinoline-2- and quinoline-8-carboxylic acids have also been described. These studies yielding promising results, we thought that there was a ground for immediate extension of our vistas of investigation into the pyridine carboxylic acids. The encouraging and extensive studies on the oxo-vanadium(IV) complexes of the pyridine carboxylic acids² also inspired us to initiate a similar effort with oxo-molybdenum(V). The present report will include the following pyridine carboxylic acids:

The inherent difficulty of using water as a possible solvent medium naturally made our studies more limited compared to oxo-vanadium(IV) situation. Moreover, the ligands having smaller weighing factor than the quinoline carboxylic acids isolation of the complexes proved somewhat difficult.

A filtered anhydrous alcoholic solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_2]$ (i.e. of MoOCl_2) reacts in CO_2 atmosphere with excess of picolinic acid to provide an intense maroon-red product, which has been identified as $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{Pic})_2]$. This is alcohol soluble and parallel in properties to $\text{MoOCl}(\text{Q}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{HCl}$ described in our earlier paper. The complex is almost diamagnetic and the authenticity of oxidation state +5 has been verified through redox titration with ferric alum and permanganate. This points to considerable spⁿ pairing due to quite an

1. Dutta and Chatterjee, this series, Part I.

2. Dutta and Ghosh, This *Journal* (in press)

extent of polymerisation in the system. The diamagnetism probably indicates polymerisation through a six co-ordinated chlorine bridged system, which is often possible with molybdenum.

Instead of using picolinic acid in excess, when one uses molybdenum and picolinic acid in the (1:1) ratio in anhydrous alcohol and then introduces half mole of o-phenanthroline, one obtains a highly crystalline, intense maroon coloured compound. Analyses indicate this to be $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{Pic}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$ or $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{Pic})_2(\text{O-Phen})]$. Similar compounds are obtained with quinolinic acid, $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{Nic}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$ or $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{Nic})_2(\text{O-Phen})]$. With pyridine 2,6-dicarboxylic acid, the composition, of necessity, due to tridentate behaviour of the ligand, gets modified to $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{Lut}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$ or $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{Lut})_2(\text{O-Phen})]$. The colour of the first two complexes is maroon and the others deep-red. They are very nearly diamagnetic, leading to the suggestion of bridged structure which can stand for considerable spin pairing.

We had earlier a very extensive series of compounds with quinoline carboxylic acids namely, $(\text{MoO}_2\text{Q.X})$ (where QH=Quinoline carboxylic acid and X = a heterocyclic base or thiourea). Similar studies with all the pyridine carboxylic acids revealed the reactions proceeding in a comparable manner with the heterocyclic bases though isolation was not possible, presumably due to a high solubility of the complex in the reaction medium. Attempts to precipitate with other non-aqueous solvent did not materialise. However, when thiourea was used as a substitute for the heterocyclic bases, the resulting complexes had much lower solubility and isolation became possible. Determination of oxidation state (after correction for a blank) once again identified the complexes as derivatives of oxomolybdenum(V). Again the complexes are diamagnetic, indicating spin pairing and hence to polymerisation in the system.

While working in aqueous medium or aqueous alcoholic medium, we obtained with picolinic acid and nicotinic acid, orange to light orange coloured crystalline products of the formula $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{Pic})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The complexes are again diamagnetic, indicating spin

TABLE I
Oxidation number & magnetic measurements
Temp. = 30°.

Compounds	Oxidation number	Diamagnetic correction $\times 10^6$	corr $\lambda \times 10^6$	* μ_{eff} (B. M.)
1. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	+5.0	—	—	Diamag.
2. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_3\text{N}_2\text{S})]$	+4.8	—	—	"
3. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)]$	+5.2	—	—	"
4. $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$	+4.98	152.5	49.3	0.34
5. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	+4.9	—	—	Diamag.
6. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$	+5.2	—	—	"
7. $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$	+5.0	—	—	"
8. $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}) \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\text{O-Phen})]$	4.85	—	—	"

* Calculated from $\lambda_{\text{m}}(\text{corr})$, using Curie equation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84(\lambda_{\text{m}}\text{XT})^{\frac{1}{2}}$

FIG. 1. Reflectance spectra of $[MoOCl_2(QuinH)_0.5(O-Phen)]$.

pairing. Strong IR band around $970-975\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are truly indicative of $Mo=O$ species rather than $O=Mo=O$. This favours a μ -dioxo bridged structure:

The complexes, being all insoluble in common organic solvents, we obtained a few reflectance spectra. These are given in Table II. The electronic spectra of $[MoOCl_2]^{2-}$ has been interpreted in terms of orbital interaction of molybdenum and oxygen with the ligands. Three d-d transitions are possible. Two d-d transitions are often observed ($dxy \rightarrow dxz$; dyz ; $dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$), but the third one ($dxy \rightarrow dz^2$) is sometimes covered by the intense charge-transfer band tailing into the visible.

TABLE II

Diffuse Reflectance Spectra of the Complexes

Complex	$\lambda_{max}(\mu)$	Wave ν numbers (cm^{-1})	Probable assignment
$[MoOCl_2(QuinH)_0.5(O-Phen)]$	700-to	14,285 to	$dxy \rightarrow dxz$, dyz
	725	13,790	
	500 to	20,000 to	$dxy \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$
	550	19,180	
	425 to 437	23,530 to 22,883	
$[MoOCl_2(Pic)_0.5(O-Phen)]$	775	12,800	$dxy \rightarrow dxz$, dyz
	425	23,500	$dxy \rightarrow dz^2$
$[MoO_2(Pic)] \cdot H_2O$	700	14,290	$dxy \rightarrow dxz$, dyz

The charge transfer transitions involve excitation of an electron from the ligand filled π -bonding molecular orbital (associated with oxygen) to the metal d-orbitals⁴⁻⁶. The electronic spectra of $[Mo_2O_2Cl_4(QuinH)_2(O-Phen)]$ shows absorption bands in the usual

- Mitchell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 963.
- Horner and Tyree Jr., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 1, 122.
- Allan and Neumann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 4, 1612.
- Baillin and Jonassen, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 99.

ranges. The corresponding complex with picolinic acid shows the first band at the expected range but the second is not clearly discerned probably being masked by the band at 425m μ . With the $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{Pic})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ the Band I is shown but the Band II and Band III are both masked by the intense charge transfer bands originating in the ultraviolet. In view of the complexes showing diamagnetic properties, it is believed that singlet ground state exists. Although our earlier interpretation is based on monomeric form, the present complexes need to be treated on dimer molecular orbitals giving rise to transitions spread over two oxo-molybdenum(V) units^{6a}.

All the complexes exhibit strong, sharp absorption bands in the IR around 970-980 cm^{-1} , typical of a metal=oxygen bond⁷⁻⁹. As suggested in the preceding part elaborate magnetic susceptibility measurements are deemed essential in order that the mechanism of the spin pairing in the complexes can be understood.

EXPERIMENTAL

Picolinic acid was prepared by permanganate oxidation of α -picoline by following standard procedure⁹. The lutidinic acid was obtained from lutidine(B.D.H) according to the usual procedure¹⁰. Quinolinic acid was prepared by oxidising oxine (8-hydroxyquinoline) with fuming HNO_3 ($d=1.52$). All refluxing was carried out on sand bath and no special precaution against air or moisture was undertaken.

(a). *Oxo-Chloro-bispicolinate molybdenum(V) (maroon)*.—Picolinic acid (.6g) dissolved in anhydrous alcohol (10 ml) was deaerated by passing CO_2 gas for about 30 minutes. To this solution $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1.30g), dissolved in anhydrous alcohol (20 ml) and filtered to remove NH_4Cl , was added. Immediately a deep maroon coloured precipitate settled while CO_2 gas passed through along with cooling of the reaction vessel. After 20 minutes the reaction product was transferred on to a sintered funnel and filtered in CO_2 atmosphere, finally dried in a vacuum desiccator. Found: Mo 25.0%; N, 0.6%; Cl, 9.2%. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$ requires Mo, 24.54%; N, 7.15%; Cl, 9.06%.

(b). *Thiourea-dioxo-picolinate-molybdenum(V) (orange)*.—Picolinic acid (3g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15 ml), was added to the clear brown aqueous alcoholic solution (15 ml) of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (.85g) and the mixture refluxed for 15-20 minutes. To this mixture thiourea (4.0 g), dissolved in rectified spirit (20 ml) was added and the mixture was further refluxed for 20 minutes. The orange crystals were filtered from cold solution, washed repeatedly with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 30.1%; N, 13.4%; S, 9.9%. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S})]$ requires Mo, 30.00%; N, 13.54%; S, 10.32%.

(c). *Dioxo-Picolinate-Molybdenum(V), monohydrate (orange)*.—Picolinic acid (.5g), dissolved in water (15 ml) was deaerated by passing CO_2 gas for about 30 minutes. To this solution, $(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{MoOCl}_5)$ (.65g) dissolved in water(15ml), was added while CO_2 passed through the solution. The orange crystalline product obtained on standing were filtered

6a. Gray, Personal Communication.

7. Barraclough, Lewis and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.

8. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 546.

9. Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. II, p. 210 (1947).

10. Banerjee and Ray, *this Journal*, 1958, 34, 207.

after 3-4 hrs.; washed with water and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 36.02%; N, 5.50%; H_2O , 6.2%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})]$ H_2O requires: Mo, 35.82%; N, 5.52%; H_2O , 6.7%.

(d). $\mu\text{-O-Phenanthroline dioxo-tetrachloro-dipicolinate-di-molybdenum(V)}$ (maroon).—Picolinic acid (.3g), dissolved in anhydrous alcohol (15c.), was added to filtered dark orange solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ (.65g) in anhydrous alcohol (20 ml). The resulting deep red solution was refluxed for 20 minutes and to this solution, O-Phenanthroline (.2g), dissolved in anhydrous alcohol (10 c.c), was added and again refluxed. The deep maroon precipitate was filtered, washed repeatedly with anhydrous alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 26.0%; N, 7.10%; Cl, 18.4%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{Pic})_2(\text{O-Phen})]$ requires Mo, 24.3%; N, 7.07%; Cl, 18%.

(e). $\text{Dioxo-nicotinate Molybdenum(V), Dihydrate (orange)}$.—Nicotinic acid (.3g), dissolved in rectified spirit (15 ml), was added to the filtered, orange solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ (.65 g) in rectified spirit (15 ml). Immediately orange precipitate resulted. It was refluxed for 20 minutes, filtered, washed repeatedly with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 33.32%; N, 4.88%; H_2O (by loss at 110°) 12.10%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}) 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mo, 33.58%; N, 4.89%; H_2O , 12.58%.

(f). $\mu\text{-O-Phenanthroline-dioxo-dichloro-lutidiniate-dimolybdenum(V)}$ (Deep-red).—Lutidinic acid (.34g), dissolved in hot water (3.5 c.c), was added to filtered dark orange solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ (.65g) in anhydrous alcohol (15 ml). The resulting red solution was refluxed for 20 minutes and to this solution O-Phenanthroline (.2g) in anhydrous alcohol (10 ml) was added and again refluxed. Immediately deep red precipitate resulted. This was filtered, washed repeatedly with anhydrous alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: Mo, 25.0%; N, 7.0%; Cl, 9.1%. $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})(\text{O-Phen})$ requires Mo, 24.85%; N, 6.96%; Cl, 8.81%.

(g). $\mu\text{-O-Phenanthroline-dioxo-tetrachloro-bisquinolinato di-molybdenum(V)}$ (maroon)—was obtained as above using quinolinic acid in place of lutidinic acid. Found: Mo, 22.4%; N, 6.5%; Cl, 16.6%. $[(\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}))_2(\text{O-Phen})]$ requires Mo, 21.91%; N, 6.36%; Cl, 16.21%.

(h). $\mu\text{-O-Phenanthroline-dioxo tetrachloro-bisnicotinate di-molybdenum(V)}$ —was obtained as above using nicotinic acid in place of quinolinic acid. Found: Mo, 23.80%; N, 7.13%; Cl, 18.42%. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{O-Phen})]$ requires Mo, 24.30%; N, 7.07%; Cl, 18.0%.

Analytical methods—Molybdenum content was determined by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 and then precipitating with oxine and weighing as $[(\text{MoO}_2(\text{Oxin}))_2]$. Nitrogen was estimated by Combustion technique. Chloride was estimated by way of double precipitation. Sulphur content was estimated by oxidising the complex with alkali, sodium peroxide and finally weighing as BaSO_4 .

Magnetic measurements—The magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy method using a semimicro Mettler balance for measuring the difference in weight and with a field strength of 8.57×10^5 gauss. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood¹¹.

The Infrared spectra were scanned on a Beckman IR -4 Infrared spectrophotometer using KBr disc technique or as Nujol mull.

11, Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", p. 91. (1958).

Oxidation state of molybdenum in the complexes was determined by dissolving a known weight of the sample in excess of acidified ferric alum solution under magnetic stirring in a stoppered flask.

After complete dissolution (which sometimes needed more than an hour), the ferrous content was determined by usual permanganate titration (Table-J). A blank was also run.

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